

On Analytic Functions defined by Combination of Operators

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Abstract: In this work, we introduce a new class of analytic functions defined by a combination of two operator. We obtain univalence condition of the new class, its integral representations, sufficient inclusion conditions and coefficient inequalities.

Key words: Analytic functions, starlike, bounded turning and univalent functions.

1. Introduction

Let A denote the class of analytic functions of the form

$$f(z) = z + a_2z^2 + a_3z^3 + \dots \quad (1)$$

in the unit disk $\{U = |z| < 1\}$. Let P denote the class of the functions

$$p(z) = 1 + c_1z + c_2z^2 + \dots \quad (2)$$

analytic in U , satisfying $Re p(z) > 0$ and by $P(\beta)$ if $p(z) > \beta$ for some real number $0 \leq \beta < 1$.

It is well-known that $f(z) \in A$ is a starlike function of order β , if

$$Re \frac{zf'(z)}{f(z)} \in p(\beta).$$

denoted as $S^*(\beta)$ (see [18]) and $Ref'(z) \in p(\beta)$ denoted as $R(\beta)$ referred to as the class of bounded turning of order β , (see [17]).

In [1], Abdulhalim generalized the class of bazilevic function consisting of functions satisfying the geometric condition

$$Re \frac{D^n f(z)^\alpha}{z^\alpha} > 0, z \in U. \quad (3)$$

denoted as $B_n(\alpha)$, where $D^n f(z) = D(D^{n-1}f(z))$, $n \in \mathbb{N}_0 = \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$ and proved that the class contains only univalent functions in the unit disk.

A further generalization, $T_n^\alpha(\beta)$, was introduced by Opoola [11] which consists of functions satisfying the geometric condition

$$\frac{D^n f(z)^\alpha}{\alpha^n z^\alpha} > \beta.$$

He proved the inclusion property and the univalence of functions in the class.

Using the salagean differential operator $D^n f(z)$ and and inverse of integral operator

$$\mathcal{L}_{\sigma,\gamma} f(z) = \frac{(\alpha + \gamma)^{-\sigma} t^{\gamma-1}}{z^\gamma \Gamma - \sigma} \int_0^z (\log \frac{z}{t})^{-\sigma-1} f(t)^\lambda dt.$$

(see [8], [16]), on $f(z)^\alpha$, we have

$$D^n(\mathcal{L}_{\sigma,\gamma} f(z)^\alpha) = z^\alpha \alpha^n + \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \left(\frac{\alpha + \gamma + k - 1}{\alpha + \gamma} \right)^\sigma (\alpha + k - 1)^n A_k(\alpha) z^{\alpha+k-1}. \quad (4)$$

where A_k for $k = 2, 3, \dots$ depends on the coefficients a_k of $f(z)$ and the index α .

We denote

$$\mathcal{L}_{\sigma,\gamma}(D^n f(z)^\alpha) = D^n(\mathcal{L}_{\sigma,\gamma} f(z)^\alpha) = L_{\sigma,\gamma}^n f(z)^\alpha. \quad (5)$$

$n \in N \cup \{0\}, \sigma > 0, \gamma > -1, \alpha > 0$.

Remark 1.1. $L_{1,0}^n = D^{n+1} f(z)^\alpha, L_{1,0}^0 = Df(z)^\alpha = z f'(z)^\alpha$. If $\alpha = 1$, then $L_{1,0}^0 = z f'(z)$.

From the series expansions of the operator $\mathcal{L}_{\sigma,\gamma}$ on $f(z)^\alpha$, we have the recursive relation

$$z(\mathcal{L}_{\sigma,\gamma} f(z)^\alpha)' = (\alpha + \gamma) \mathcal{L}_{\sigma+1,\gamma} f(z)^\alpha - \gamma \mathcal{L}_{\sigma,\gamma} f(z)^\alpha. \quad (6)$$

Applying D^n on (6), we have

$$L_{\sigma,\gamma}^{n+1} f(z)^\alpha = (\alpha + \gamma) L_{\sigma+1,\gamma}^n f(z)^\alpha - \gamma L_{\sigma,\gamma}^n f(z)^\alpha. \quad (7)$$

Using the salagean anti-derivative define as $I_n = I(I_{n-1} f(z)) = \int_0^z \frac{I_{n-1} f(t)}{t} dt$ and

$$\mathcal{J}_{\sigma,\gamma} f(z) = \frac{(\alpha + \gamma)^\sigma t^{\gamma-1}}{z^\gamma \Gamma \sigma} \int_0^z (\log \frac{z}{t})^{\sigma-1} f(t) dt, \text{ (see [8], [16]) on } f(z)^\alpha.$$

Therefore

$$I_n(\mathcal{J}_{\sigma,\gamma} f(z)^\alpha) = \frac{z^\alpha}{\alpha^n} + \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \left(\frac{\alpha + \gamma}{\alpha + \gamma + k - 1} \right)^\sigma \frac{A_k(\alpha)}{(\alpha + k - 1)^n} z^{\alpha+k-1}. \quad (8)$$

We denote

$$I_n(\mathcal{J}_{\sigma,\gamma} f(z)^\alpha) = \mathcal{J}_{\sigma,\gamma}(I_n f(z)^\alpha) = J_{\sigma,\gamma}^n f(z)^\alpha. \quad (9)$$

It can be seen that

$$L_{\sigma,\gamma}^n(J_{\sigma,\gamma}^n f(z)^\alpha) = J_{\sigma,\gamma}^n(L_{\sigma,\gamma}^n f(z)^\alpha) = f(z)^\alpha. \quad (10)$$

The concept of combining operators in theory of geometric function has been a very useful tool and this has been considered by many researchers to introduce subclasses of analytic and meromorphic functions, (see [2-7]).

Using the operator $L_{\sigma,\gamma}^n$, we introduce a new class defined as follows:

Definition 1. An analytic function $f \in A$ is said to belong to the class $B_{\sigma,\gamma}^{n,\alpha}(\beta)$ if and only if

$$\frac{L_{\sigma,\gamma}^n f(z)^\alpha}{\alpha^n z^\alpha} > \beta. \quad (11)$$

$n \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}, \sigma > 0, \gamma > -1, \alpha > 0.$

Remark 1.2. If $\sigma = 1, \gamma = 0, n = 0$ and $\alpha = 1$ we have the class of analytic function satisfying

$$\operatorname{Re} f'(z) > \beta \quad (12)$$

which is the class of functions of bounded turning of order β denoted as $R(\beta)$.

2. Preliminary Lemmas

Lemma 2.1. [9] Let $p(z)$ be holomorphic in E with $p(0) = 1$. Suppose that

$$\operatorname{Re} \left(1 + \frac{zp'(z)}{p(z)} \right) > \frac{3\beta - 1}{2\beta}.$$

Then

$$\operatorname{Re} p(z) > 2^{1-\frac{1}{\beta}}, \frac{1}{2} \leq \beta < 1, z \in U. \quad (13)$$

and the constant $2^{1-\frac{1}{\beta}}$ is the best possible.

Lemma 2.2. [10] Let $u = u_1 + u_2i, v = v_1 + v_2i$ and $\Phi(u, v)$ a complex valued function satisfying

(i) $\Phi(u, v)$ is continuous in a domain Ω of C^2 .

(ii) $(1, 0) \in \Omega$ and $\operatorname{Re} \Phi(1, 0) > 0$.

(iii) $\operatorname{Re} \Phi(\beta + (1 - \beta)u_2i, v_1) \leq \beta$ when $(\beta + (1 - \beta)u_2i, v_1) \in \Omega$ If $p \in P$ such that $(p(z), zp'(z)) \in \Omega$ and $\operatorname{Re}(p(z), zp'(z)) > \beta$ for $z \in U$. Then $\operatorname{Re} p(z) > \beta$ in U .

Lemma 2.3. [12] Let $p \in P$. where $p(z) = 1 + c_1z + p_2z^2 + \dots$, then

$$|p_k| \leq 2, k = 1, 2, 3, \dots \quad (14)$$

Lemma 2.4. [11] Let $p \in P$. then for any real or complex number μ , we have sharp inequalities

$$\left| p_2 - \mu \frac{p_1^2}{2} \right| \leq 2 \max\{1, |1 - \mu|\}. \quad (15)$$

3. Main Results

Theorem 3.1. *Let $f \in B_{\sigma,\gamma}^{n,\alpha}(\beta)$, then $f(z)$ has the integral representation*

$$f(z) = J_{\sigma,\gamma}^n[\alpha^n z^n(p(z))]^{\frac{1}{\alpha}}$$

Proof. Since $f \in B_{\sigma,\gamma}^{n,\alpha}(\beta)$, then there exists $p \in P(\beta)$ such that

$$\frac{L_{\sigma,\gamma}^n f(z)^\alpha}{\alpha^n z^\alpha} = p(z)$$

and

$$L_{\sigma,\gamma}^n f(z)^\alpha = \alpha^n z^\alpha p(z)$$

applying the antiderivative operator $J_{\sigma,\gamma}^n$, we obtain

$$f(z) = J_{\sigma,\gamma}^n[\alpha^n z^n(p(z))]^{\frac{1}{\alpha}}$$

□

Theorem 3.2. *$B_{\sigma,\gamma}^{n,\alpha}(\beta) \subset T_n^\alpha(\beta)$, for $\alpha > 0$.*

Proof. Let

$$p(z) = \frac{D^n f(z)^\alpha}{\alpha^n z^\alpha}$$

Then, from (11), we obtain

$$\operatorname{Re} \left(p(z)^2 + \frac{z p(z) p'(z)}{\alpha} \right) > \beta.$$

We define

$$\Phi(u, v) = u^2 + \frac{uv}{\alpha}, \alpha > 0.$$

Clearly, $\Phi(u, v)$ satisfies the condition of Lemma 2.2. whenever $2v_1 < -(1 - \beta)(1 + u_2^2)$, we have

$$\operatorname{Re} \Phi(\beta + (1 - \beta)u_2 i, v_1) = \beta^2 - (1 - \beta)^2 u_2^2 - \frac{\beta(1 - \beta)(1 + u_2^2)}{2\alpha} < \beta < \beta.$$

Hence by lemma 2.2, we have $\operatorname{Re} p(z)$, implies that $\operatorname{Re} \frac{D^n f(z)^\alpha}{\alpha^n z^\alpha} > \beta$ and the proof completes. □

Corollary 3.1. *For $n \geq 1$, the class $B_{\sigma,\gamma}^{n,\alpha}(\beta)$ consists of univalent functions.*

Theorem 3.3. *If $f \in A$ satisfies*

$$\operatorname{Re} \left(\frac{L_{\sigma,\gamma}^{n+1} f(z)^\alpha}{L_{\sigma,\gamma}^n f(z)^\alpha} \right) > \frac{2\alpha\beta + \beta - 1}{2\beta}. \quad (16)$$

Then

$$\operatorname{Re} \frac{L_{\sigma,\gamma}^n f(z)^\alpha}{\alpha^n z^n} > 2^{1-\frac{1}{\beta}}, \frac{1}{2} \leq \beta < 1, z \in \mathbb{U}.$$

Proof. Let

$$\frac{L_{\sigma,\gamma}^{n+1}f(z)^\alpha}{\alpha^n z^n} = p(z),$$

then we have that

$$\frac{zp'(z)}{p(z)} = \frac{L_{\sigma,\gamma}^{n+1}f(z)^\alpha}{L_{\sigma,\gamma}^n f(z)^\alpha} - \alpha.$$

By the condition of the theorem,

$$\operatorname{Re} \left(1 + \frac{zp'(z)}{p(z)} \right) = \operatorname{Re} \left(\frac{L_{\sigma,\gamma}^{n+1}f(z)^\alpha}{L_{\sigma,\gamma}^n f(z)^\alpha} - \alpha + 1 \right) > \frac{3\beta - 1}{2\beta}$$

and this is equivalent to

$$\operatorname{Re} \left(\frac{L_{\sigma,\gamma}^{n+1}f(z)^\alpha}{L_{\sigma,\gamma}^n f(z)^\alpha} \right) > \frac{2\alpha\beta + \beta - 1}{2\beta}.$$

Thus by lemma 2.1, $\operatorname{Re}p(z) > 2^{1-\frac{1}{\beta}}$, $\frac{1}{\beta} \leq \beta < 1$, $z \in \mathbb{U}$. □

Corollary 3.2. *If $f \in A$ satisfies the condition, then $f \in B_{\sigma,\gamma}^{n,\alpha}(2^{1-\frac{1}{\beta}})$.*

If $n = 0$, $\alpha = 0$, we have

Corollary 3.3. *Suppose*

$$\operatorname{Re} \left(\frac{zf''(z)}{f'(z)} + 1 \right) > \frac{\beta - 1}{2\beta}.$$

Then

$$\operatorname{Re}f'(z) > 2^{1-\frac{1}{\beta}}.$$

If $n = 0$, $\alpha = 1/2$, we have

Corollary 3.4. *Suppose*

$$\operatorname{Re} \left(\frac{zf''(z)}{f'(z)} + 1 \right) > \frac{3\beta - 1}{2\beta}.$$

Then

$$\operatorname{Re}f'(z) > 2^{1-\frac{1}{\beta}}.$$

If $n = 0$, $\alpha = 1$ and $\beta = 1/2$, we have

Corollary 3.5. *Suppose*

$$\operatorname{Re} \left(\frac{zf''(z)}{f'(z)} + 1 \right) > \frac{1}{2}$$

. Then

$$\operatorname{Re}f'(z) > \frac{1}{2}.$$

Theorem 3.4. *Let $f \in B_{\sigma,\gamma}^{n,\alpha}(\beta)$, then*

$$|a_2| \leq \frac{2\alpha^{n-1}(1-\beta)}{(\alpha+1)^n} \left(\frac{\alpha+\gamma}{\alpha+\gamma+1} \right)^\sigma.$$

$$|a_3| \leq \frac{\alpha^{n-1}(\alpha+\gamma)^\sigma(1-\beta)}{(\alpha+2)^n(\alpha+\gamma+2)^\sigma} \max\{1, |\mathbf{M}_1|\} \quad (17)$$

where $\mathbf{M}_1 = \frac{2(\alpha+1)^{2n}(\alpha+\gamma+1)^{2\sigma} + (1-\alpha)\alpha^n(\alpha+\gamma)^\sigma(\alpha+2)^n(\alpha+\gamma+2)^\sigma}{(\alpha+1)^{2n}(\alpha+\gamma+1)^{2\sigma}}$

The bounds are best possible. Equalities are obtained also by

$$\begin{aligned} f(z)^\alpha &= \left\{ J_{\sigma,\gamma}^n \left[\alpha^n z^\alpha \left(\beta + (1-\beta) \frac{1+z}{1-z} \right) \right] \right\}^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} \\ &= z + \frac{\alpha^n}{(\alpha+1)^n} \left(\frac{\alpha+\gamma}{\alpha+\gamma+1} \right)^\sigma z^2 + \\ &\quad \frac{\alpha^n(\alpha+\gamma)^\sigma}{(\alpha+2)^n(\alpha+\gamma+2)^\sigma} \left\{ \frac{(\alpha+1)^{2n}(\alpha+\gamma+1)^{2\sigma} + (1-\alpha)\alpha^n(\alpha+\gamma)^\sigma(\alpha+2)^n(\alpha+\gamma+2)^\sigma}{(\alpha+1)^{2n}(\alpha+\gamma+1)^{2\sigma}} \right\} z^3 + \dots \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let $f \in B_{\sigma,\lambda}^{n,\alpha}(\lambda)$, then there exists $p \in P_\beta$ such that

$$\frac{L_{\sigma,\gamma}^n f(z)^\alpha}{\alpha^n z^\alpha} = p(z) = 1 + (1-\beta)c_1 z + (1-\beta)c_2 z^2 + (1-\beta)c_3 z^3 + \dots \quad (18)$$

$$L_{\sigma,\gamma}^n f(z)^\alpha = \alpha^n z^\alpha + \alpha^n(1-\beta)c_1 z^{\alpha+1} + \alpha^n(1-\beta)c_2 z^{\alpha+2} + \alpha^n(1-\beta)c_3 z^{\alpha+3} + \alpha^{n-1}(1-\beta)c_4 z^{\alpha+4} + \dots$$

Using the anti-derivative of the operator $L_{\sigma,\gamma}^n$ denoted as $J_{\sigma,\gamma}^n$, we have that

$$\begin{aligned} f(z)^\alpha &= z^\alpha + \frac{\alpha^n(1-\beta)}{(\alpha+1)^n} \left(\frac{\alpha+\gamma}{\alpha+\gamma+1} \right)^\sigma c_1 z^{\alpha+1} + \frac{\alpha^n(1-\beta)}{(\alpha+2)^n} \left(\frac{\alpha+\gamma}{\alpha+\gamma+2} \right)^\sigma c_2 z^{\alpha+2} \\ &\quad + \frac{\alpha^n(1-\beta)}{(\alpha+3)^n} \left(\frac{\alpha+\gamma}{\alpha+\gamma+3} \right)^\sigma c_3 z^{\alpha+3} + \frac{\alpha^n(1-\beta)}{(\alpha+4)^n} \left(\frac{\alpha+\gamma}{\alpha+\gamma+4} \right)^\sigma c_4 z^{\alpha+4} \dots \end{aligned}$$

Given that

$$\begin{aligned} f(z)^\alpha &= z^\alpha + \alpha a_2 z^{\alpha+1} + \left(\alpha a_3 + \frac{\alpha(\alpha-1)}{2} a_2^2 \right) z^{\alpha+2} + \left(\alpha a_4 + \alpha(\alpha-1)a_2 a_3 + \frac{\alpha(\alpha-1)(\alpha-2)}{6} a_2^3 \right) z^{\alpha+3} \\ &\quad + \left(\alpha a_5 + \alpha(\alpha-1)a_2 a_4 + \frac{\alpha(\alpha-1)}{2} a_3^2 + \frac{\alpha(\alpha-1)(\alpha-2)}{2} a_2^2 a_3 + \frac{\alpha(\alpha-1)(\alpha-2)(\alpha-3)}{12} a_2^4 \right) z^{\alpha+4} + \dots \end{aligned}$$

By comparing the coefficient , we have

$$a_2 = \frac{\alpha^{n-1}}{(\alpha+1)^n} \left(\frac{\alpha+\gamma}{\alpha+\gamma+1} \right)^\sigma c_1$$

By Lemma 2.3, we obtained the bound of a_2 , also

$$a_3 = \frac{\alpha^n(\alpha + \gamma)^\sigma(1 - \beta)}{(\alpha + 2)^n(\alpha + \gamma + 2)^\sigma} \left[c_2 - \frac{\alpha^n(\alpha - 1)(\alpha + \gamma)^\sigma(\alpha + 2)^n(\alpha + \gamma + 2)^\sigma c_1^2}{(\alpha + 1)^{2n}(\alpha + \gamma + 1)^{2\sigma}} \frac{c_1^2}{2} \right]$$

By Lemma 2.4 and with $\rho = \frac{\alpha^n(\alpha - 1)(\alpha + \gamma)^\sigma(\alpha + 2)^n(\alpha + \gamma + 2)^\sigma}{(\alpha + 1)^{2n}(\alpha + \gamma + 1)^{2\sigma}}$, we obtained the bound on the third coefficient of these function. By letting

$$p(z) = \beta + (1 - \beta) \frac{1 + z}{1 - z}$$

from the integral representation we have the equality attained by the extremal function given. \square

Theorem 3.5. *Let $f \in B_{\sigma, \gamma}^{n, \alpha}(\beta)$. Then*

$$|a_3 - \rho a_2^2| \leq \frac{\alpha^{n-1}(1 - \beta)(\alpha + \gamma)^\sigma}{(\alpha + 2)^n(\alpha + \gamma + 2)^\sigma} \max\{1, |\mathbf{M}_2|\} \quad (19)$$

$$\text{where } \mathbf{M}_2 = \frac{2(\alpha + 1)^{2n}(\alpha + \gamma + 1)^{2\sigma} + (1 + 2\rho - \alpha)\alpha^{n-1}(\alpha + \gamma)^\sigma(\alpha + 2)^n(\alpha + \gamma + 2)^\sigma}{(\alpha + 1)^{2n}(\alpha + \gamma + 1)^{2\sigma}}$$

Proof. From the computation and by comparing coefficient with respect to z , then

$$a_2 = \frac{\alpha^{n-1}(1 - \beta)}{(\alpha + 1)^n} \left(\frac{\alpha + \gamma}{\alpha + \gamma + 1} \right)^\sigma c_1 \quad (20)$$

and

$$a_3 = \frac{\alpha^n(\alpha + \gamma)^\sigma c_2}{(\alpha + 2)^n(\alpha + \gamma + 2)^\sigma} + \frac{(1 - \alpha)\alpha^{2(n-2)}(\alpha + \gamma)^{2\sigma} c_1^2}{(\alpha + 1)^{2n}(\alpha + \gamma + 1)^{2\sigma}} \frac{c_1^2}{2} \quad (21)$$

Hence

$$|a_3 - \rho a_2^2| = \frac{\alpha^{n-1}(\alpha + \gamma)^\sigma}{(\alpha + 2)^n(\alpha + \gamma + 2)^\sigma} c_2 - \frac{(\alpha - 1 + 2\rho)(\alpha + 2)^n \alpha^{n-1}(\alpha + \gamma)^\sigma(\alpha + \gamma + 2)^\sigma c_1^2}{(\alpha + 1)^{2n}(\alpha + \gamma + 1)^{2\sigma}} \frac{c_1^2}{2} \quad (22)$$

by lemma 2.4 we have the required inequality. \square

4. Conclusion

In this work we have been able to determine the univalence condition of the new class, its integral representations, sufficient inclusion conditions and coefficient inequalities of a subclass of analytics functions defined by combination of two operators.

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